

Design and Construction of Digital Distance Measuring Instrument for Science and Engineering Application

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Abstract

This article presents the development of a digital distance measuring device with an ultrasonic sensor (HC-SR04) and an Arduino microcontroller. The device has the potential to substitute the traditional devices such as manual tape measures with higher accuracy, speed, and data logging capability. The circuit was modeled on Eagle software, the PCB design was done, microcontroller was coded, and the 3D case design on SolidWorks. Prototype accuracy, precision, and speed were tested and proved to provide dramatic improvement compared to conventional methods. The instrument provides a high degree of accuracy for the range of measurement (2-400 cm) and provides quick distance measurement with precision of 97-100%. The compact and user-friendly nature of the instrument makes it suitable for various applications across industries like robotics, construction, and industrial automation.

Keywords: Accuracy, Distance, Digital, Precision, Prototype, Sensor

1.0 Introduction

A measuring instrument is a device for measuring physical quantity in the physical science, quality assurance and engineering [1]. Measurement is the activity of obtaining and comparing physical quantity of real-world objects and events [2].

Measurement of distances has been a critical human need since ancient times [4]. From basic surveying and construction to modern applications in robotics, navigation, and scientific research, accurate and fast distance measurement is crucial [3]. Traditional methods of distance measurement are often hampered by limited range, poor precision, slow velocity, and limited functionality [5]. Such limitations can hinder efficiency and accuracy in a wide range of scientific and engineering applications. The overall objective of this research is to develop a digital distance measuring instrument that surpasses the limitations of the traditional ones as well as a low-cost and effective prototype of the device proposed. The successful fabrication of the digital distance measuring device has far-reaching implications since it highly

improves the effectiveness of distance measuring functions in various fields. To design, fabricate, and verify a digital distance measuring device was the objective of this study. The scope includes the Selection of appropriate sensors and technologies, Instrument hardware and software design, Development and construction of a prototype instrument, Evaluation of prototype performance in controlled environments and Investigation of potential applications in selected scientific and engineering fields.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the device

The microprocessor receives the objects information through the ultrasonic sensor. The touch button enables the user to provide a reference frame while the display serves as an output provide the distance between the object and the reference frame as illustrated in the figure 2.1 below.

Figure 2.1: Block diagram of digital measuring device

Table 2.1: List of electronics components used

S/N	Materials	Specification
1	Ultrasonic sensor	HC-SR04
2	Microprocessor	ATMEGA168-20P
3	LED	RGB
4	Display	1602LCD module
5	Resistor	220, 1k, 10k
6	Sound	Active buzzer element
7	Casing	Plastic and screws
8	Button	Touch sensor
9	Clock	Crystal
10	Cutting and milling	CNC machine

2.2 Simulation of the Device

All the connections were simulated using eagle hyperdex software as illustrated in figure 2.2 below.

The Trig and echo digital pins of ultrasonic sensor HC-SR04 were connected to Pin 4(PD2) and Pin 5 (PD3) of the ATMEGA168-20P. The LCD is connected using IC2 protocol where all pins of the LCD is connected to IC2 chip given the output of 4pins. The SDA is connected to pin 27(PC 4) and SCL pin is connected to pin 28(PC 5) on the ATMEGA168-20P. The Crystal is connected to pin 9 and 10 of the ATMEGA. A capacitor was connected to the crystal in one terminal and to the ground on the other terminal. The touch button is connected to pin 1(PC6) of the ATMEGA168-20P and to the ground on the other terminal. The buzzer is connected to 5V, and the emitter of the transistor while the base is connected to the resistor which is connected to the pin 14(PB0) of the ATMEGA168-20P. The input pin of the voltage regulator was connected to the voltage source while the GND was connected to the ground and the output pin is connected to the VCC of the ATMEGA168-20.

Figure: 3.5 Functionality test of the device

3.0 Results

3.1 Results of Comparative Analysis Between the Digital Distance and Measuring Tape

From Table 3.1, it is much faster to measure distance between two points using the device compared to the traditional measuring. Its takes just a second to measure 300cm using the constructed

device compared to the measuring tape which takes up to 11.39s to measure.

The device was tested 25 times for accuracy analysis (Table 3.2). The result shows the accuracy of the device reduce slightly with the increase in distance but remain highly accurate with the accuracy of 97% at 400cm.

Table 3.1: Average Time Taken to Take Measurement on A Real-Life Scenario

Distance Measured (cm)	Ultrasonic Distance Measuring Device Prototype	Measuring Tape
25	1 s	2.07 s
50	1 s	2.28 s
100	1 s	3.08 s
200	1 s	9.17 s
300	1 s	11.39 s
400	1 s	N/A

Table 3.2: Data of Ultrasonic Distance Measuring Device Prototype’s Precision and Accuracy under 25 attempts

Distance Measured (cm)	Accuracy [25 attempts]	Precision [25 attempts]
25	100% [25/25]	100% [25/25]
50	99% [25/25]	100% [25/25]
100	98% [25/25]	100% [25/25]
200	98% [25/25]	100% [25/25]
300	97% [25/25]	100% [25/25]
400	97% [25/25]	100% [25/25]

4.0 Discussions

The developed ultrasonic distance meter with HC-SR04 sensor and ATMEGA168-20P microcontroller has proved to provide accurate and

consistent distance measurements from 2 to 400 cm. The features include high accuracy ($\pm 3\%$) and 1 cm resolution, with a high rate of update equal to 10 Hz and low power consumption (20 mA). Its compact size and simple-to-use interface make it well suited for a variety of uses, such as obstacle detection,

navigation, and level measurement. The non-contact sensor minimizes wear and tear, and the low price gives a cost-saving alternative to more expensive laser-based distance sensors. In addition, its compatibility with numerous microcontrollers and platforms makes it easily integratable into systems to provide a broader range of applications in robotics, industrial automation, surveying, and security systems.

The experimental results presented in Tables 3.1 and 3.2 validate the prototype's operational ability and its efficiency in measuring distances. One of the self-evident advantages is the minimal measurement time; it only takes one second to measure distances up to 400 cm, a stark difference with the traditional measuring tape that took up to 11.39 seconds for 300 cm. This is an incredible reduction in measurement time. As for precision, the device was able to produce 100% precision for all test distances every one of the time. Precision decreased slightly with increased distance but remained strongly accurate at 97% for 400 cm. Results indicate a solid and stable performance in the range desired.

A few other identical ultrasonic distance measuring tools have been developed by other researchers with the same HC-SR04 sensor because it is inexpensive and simple to utilize. For instance, [3] has developed a similar system which can be used by robots to move around with an accuracy of $\pm 5\%$ in a limited range up to 200 cm. Their circuit, however, used another microcontroller, which can have different processing rates and memory sizes compared to the ATMEGA168-20P. Another study by [5] focused on making a non-contact liquid level sensor, which also used the HC-SR04. While their primary interest was level measurement and not any distance in general, they reported comparable accuracy readings up to 300 cm but with a slower rate of data acquisition than our 10 Hz.

Our device stands out for its optimized hardware-software integration, and it has a consistent 1-second measurement time across its entire range of operation. The steady pace in Table 3.1 is a noticeable improvement over the majority of mere implementations which can find it sluggish at times or have measurement times that change depending on distance. While some commercial high-end ultrasonic sensors can report higher accuracies (e.g., $\pm 1\%$), they can be significantly more expensive. For example, ultrasonic transducers intended for

industrial use utilized in production processes can yield sub-millimeter accuracy but cost orders of magnitude more than the HC-SR04.

5.0 Conclusion

This study successfully developed a prototype of a digital distance measuring device utilizing an ultrasonic sensor, an ATMEGA168-20P microcontroller, and supporting electronics. The device was designed, simulated, and fabricated using readily available components and open-source software like Eagle CAD and Arduino IDE. The prototype demonstrated high accuracy and precision in measuring distances up to 400 cm, with an average accuracy of 97% across 25 trials. Notably, the device significantly outperformed traditional measuring tapes in terms of speed, requiring only 1 second to measure distances compared to several seconds for manual methods. The user-friendly interface, incorporating a touch button for reference frame setting and an LCD display for real-time distance readings, enhances ease of use. Furthermore, the device's portability, facilitated by a custom-designed case, makes it suitable for various field applications. This project successfully demonstrates the feasibility of developing a cost-effective and efficient digital distance measuring device.

6.0 Recommendation

- **Implement Calibration Routines:** Develop a procedure to calibrate the device regularly to ensure consistent and accurate measurements. This could involve comparing measurements to a known standard, such as a calibrated measuring tape.
- **Incorporate Memory Storage:** Enable the device to store measured values for later analysis or retrieval.
- **Implement Data Logging:** Allow for continuous data recording for applications like monitoring object movement or environmental changes.
- **Enable Bluetooth Connectivity:** Integrate Bluetooth to transmit data wirelessly to other devices, such as smartphones or computers, for data analysis, visualization, and remote control.
- **Add Angle Measurement:** Explore the possibility of incorporating an angle sensor to

measure both distance and angle, providing more comprehensive spatial information.

7.0 References

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